

nextGEMS

Next Generation Earth Modelling Systems

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About this document

Report on the conducted knowledge coproduction activities with an update of the coproduction plan.

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WP10

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1 Executive summary

This deliverable focuses on the ongoing co-production activities deployed to specifically fulfill objective O3 (ii):

O3: to build new, more integrated, communities of ESM users by: (ii) exploiting the affinity between what people experience and what SR-ESMs simulate (i.e., events, in addition to statistics) to more directly involve non-scientific users in model development, thereby fostering Knowledge Coproduction.

Between the time span of month 5 (submission of the Coproduction plan) to month 24 (Interim report on Knowledge Coproduction activities), there have been several activities conducted in this regard. This report describes these activities, which involve the search for applications of the SR-ESM data outputs for real-world applications related to the two selected Societal Problems: renewable energy and fisheries. All work packages have been involved with different degrees of intensity in the conduction of these activities, which shows a high degree of cohesion within the nextGEMS research community.

2 Conclusion & Results

The hackathons and the co-production activities conducted up until month 24 can be evaluated positively. In regards to knowledge co-production, the most important lessons learnt are:

- A purpose conscious approach on user and stakeholder selection and engagement has proven to be a sound strategy to explore forms in which the scientific outputs of nextGEMS may positively support the science-policy-society interface;
- The low technical readiness of scientific outputs does not preclude initiating advanced forms of knowledge co-production;
- Transdisciplinary forms of science as fostered in EU-funded research – with the interaction between scientists of different disciplines, users and stakeholders; and finally,
- Issue-centred co-production activities support the exploitation of the affinity between what people experience and what SR-ESMs simulate.

3 Project objectives

The following table lists the overall objectives of nextGEMS. Objectives that the current report contributes to are flagged with yes.

Specific objectives of the project	Contribution of this deliverable?
O1	
To develop two SR-ESMs for applications	
(i) by demonstrating their capacity to more realistically represent the coupled (land-ocean-atmosphere) climate system, also through an ability to better leverage observations;	no
(ii) by performing the first global multi-decadal (30 y) SR-ESM based climate projections, testing for out-of-sample climate trajectories, i.e., surprises, and thereby giving a new perspective on uncertainty; and	no
(iii) by expanding their scope to begin more physically coupling 'Earth-system' processes, including the carbon cycle and the atmospheric aerosol	no
O2	
To use SR-ESMs to test emerging and long-standing hypotheses underpinning our understanding of climate change:	
(i) that convective organization contributes importantly to Earth's energy budget and the strength of cloud feedbacks;	no
(ii) that a more explicit representation of cloud-aerosol interactions mutes aerosol-radiative forcing;	no
(iii) that 2 km to 200 km scale atmospheric and oceanic circulations are of leading order importance for air-sea fluxes in the tropics, thereby influencing not only the mean tropical and mid-latitude climate, but also its variability, including extremes;	no
(iv) that storm-scale variability in weather systems and of the land surface strongly influence extra-tropical climate and extremes, for instance by conditioning circulation regimes, like blocking;	no
(v) that capturing landscape variability globally greatly improves the realism with which regional climate can be simulated; and	no

Specific objectives of the project	Contribution of this deliverable?
(vi) that storm-scale variability through its impact on hydrological extremes affects the carbon budget, with associated implications for the global carbon (emissions) stock-take.	no
O3	
To build new, more integrated, communities of ESM users by:	
(i) exploiting the necessity of developing SR-ESMs around a centralized infrastructure to create development and analysis paradigms that can more directly involve a broader and more distributed scientific community; and	yes
(ii) by exploiting the affinity between what people experience and what SR-ESMs simulate (i.e., events, in addition to statistics) to more directly involve non-scientific users in model development, thereby fostering Knowledge Coproduction.	yes

This deliverable directly contributes to the achievement of specific objectives indicated in the description of the Work Package:

Objectives of WP10	Relevance in this deliverable?
Implement, monitor and adjust an effective strategy for NextGEMS coproduction, communication & dissemination and video presence (O3)	yes
Connect model development and application communities and integrate potential users into the coproduction activities (coproduction process) (O3)	yes
Develop novel communication and dissemination forms to maximize the visibility and usability of the project and its results to target audiences (communication and dissemination) (O3)	yes

Objectives of WP10

Relevance in this deliverable?

Provide technical and policy briefings to the competent authorities to make them aware of project results (policy dissemination) (O3)

yes

4 Detailed report on the deliverable

The purpose of knowledge co-production activities in climate-related science is to address two well-recognised gaps: the usability gap and the climate action gap. The former refers to the situation by which, despite the increase in the quality of climate information, its use by societal actors has not followed suit. The latter gap is self-defining and refers to the fact that despite this available knowledge, social systems are slow in reacting to the knowns of climate evolution. Well conducted knowledge co-production activities can effectively support the reduction of both these gaps (Daly, 2021; Bruno Soares and Buontempo, 2019; Swart et al., 2017). Knowledge co-production refers thus to the collaborative effort between scientists, users and stakeholders. To ensure its success, coproduction should involve an ongoing and iterative exchange of communication, ideas, and collaboration (Bojovic et al., 2021).

In the context of nextGEMS, the primary platform for sharing knowledge and engaging in knowledge coproduction is through face-to-face hackathons. During these events, scientists share model data with participants who test and explore it to tackle real-world challenges formulated in collaboration with stakeholders. Additionally, another avenue for knowledge coproduction lies in the development of storylines, such as those concerning the two societal problems identified at the proposal stage: Renewable Energy and Fisheries.

4.1 Hackathons

Hackathons are the main meeting format in nextGEMS. During these events, participants from within and outside the project gather together in one place and code together. To date, three nextGEMS hackathons took place.

The first hackathon, focusing on the simulations from development Cycle 1, was held from 19.10.2021 to 21.10.2021 in Berlin, Germany with 81 people participating on-site and 15 people participating online. This hackathon took place shortly after the project's start and during the Covid-19 pandemic. The Cycle 2 hackathon was organized in Vienna, Austria from 26. June to 02. July 2022 with 92 participants. And the Cycle 3 hackathon, with 142 participants, took place in Madrid, Spain from 29. May to 2. June 2023.

4.1.1 User engagement

The key project users, from the energy and fishery sectors, participated in the hackathons. The nextGEMS partner IBERDROLA, as well as other renewable energy users from the Institute for Sustainable Economic Development, Vienna, took part in the Cycle 2 hackathon. Together with external PhD students from renewable energy and climate science, the representative from industry focused on the following challenge: How does the potential renewable energy output landscape change with a changing climate?

Similarly, users from the Senegalese Institute of Agricultural Research joined other project partners in the Glorious Catch Group at the Cycle 3 hackathon in Madrid, from 29 May to 3 June

2023, to specify the aim of the fisheries storyline. The hackathon in Madrid also hosted partners and stakeholders from the renewable energy sector for an on-site workshop discussing Renewable Energy storylines(see 4.2.1).

4.1.2 Assessing the co-production process in hackathons

The implementation of Objective 3 (i), to exploit the benefits of developing SR-ESMs around a centralized infrastructure to create development and analysis paradigms that can more directly involve a broader and more distributed scientific community, is one of the innovations of nextGEMS. We are conducting a study to prove the soundness of this approach to developing climate-related science and specifically models. Concretely, the Storms & Society theme (WP10) is tracking the evolution of the interactions among the Hackathon participants through Social Network Analysis (SNA). This method – and partially theory – is employed to examine the interaction patterns and network structures formed among various actors (nodes). Following each Hackathon, participants have been asked to complete a survey, wherein they assess their relationships with other Hackathon attendees. This assessment includes the evaluation of the intensity and novelty of each link. Currently, there is data for three hackathons, and the plan is to compare how the network evolves across the project over time.

The outputs of the SNA for each hackathon has been presented during the weekly office hours, now labelled as Storms & Science seminar. The comparative study has not been conducted yet, but WP10 is collaborating with an expert in SNA to be able to obtain the most from the rich data that offers the connection patterns between the hackathon participants.

4.2 Storylines

A literature review conducted at BSC, identified three different approaches to 'storylines' found in climate-related science: scenario storylines, well-known for their use in the IPCC reports; physical climate storylines (see 4.2.2); and discourse-analytical approaches (Baulenas, Versteeg, et al., 2023). They all respond to the need to link climate – and its evolution – to social systems, but they propose to do so from different perspectives and forms. The two project storylines will implement all three approaches: the renewable energy pilot study merges scenario storylines with discourse-analytical approaches, and the fisheries pilot will implement physical climate storylines.

4.2.1 Storyline of Renewable Energy pilot study

The Renewable Energy pilot study explores how the outputs from the modeling efforts can support decision-making, and especially decision-making for society such as the one conducted by national governments in the context of adapting to climate change. This pilot study has selected the National Integrated Plan on Energy and Climate, which is a legislation found in each EU Member State listing the measures to achieve the decarbonization goals for 2030. The study, using Spain as example, has been designed to co-produce qualitative storylines that depart

from this law and present different scenarios of an energy transition towards a greater role of renewable energy. The aim is to model these different storylines, using nextGEMS data outputs up until 2030, and thus investigate the climate-energy-society interactions for the different scenarios. The key of this pilot study is the co-production component, as the storylines have been co-produced with stakeholders.

As the co-production workshop aims to expand upon the existing storylines generated at the Cycle 3 hackathon in Madrid, several steps were taken in preparation. This included a literature review, a preliminary workshop, expert interviews, and meetings. We describe this next:

1. Online meeting with advanced nextGEMS energy data potential users (April 2022): 13 participants from solar and wind industry (e.g. RWE renewables, EDT, VESTAS) and research institutes (DLR, DTU, BOKU) attended the meeting to exchange ideas and plans between the climate science and RE community, i.e. what can SR-ESM offer and where do we think the nextGEMS simulations could be of interest. The meeting mainly centred around the already available products such as global wind atlas products and unavailable but interesting variables that can be obtained from nextGEMS data, such as 'rain drop size distribution change', 'equivalent energy density' or icing information.
2. Preliminary workshop with the nextGEMS scientific community (June 2022): This preliminary workshop had three objectives: (i) explore challenges and needs regarding renewable energy from different perspectives; (ii) clarify how SR-ESM can contribute to addressing them; (iii) and discuss approaches to add the "story". The workshop slides and outcomes can be found in this link: <https://t.ly/2m-EA>.
3. Literature review of grey and scientific literature (July – October 2022): the aim of this activity was to identify the discourses present in the energy sector from different perspectives, including economic rationales, environmental and social concerns, as well as socio-political understandings of the transition to renewable energy.
4. Stakeholder mapping (November – December 2022): the literature review already allowed to detect relevant actors related to renewable energy in Spain. They were listed and contacted. The stakeholder mapping followed a purposive sample based on the work published in Baulenas, Bojovic, et al., 2023, which is based on principles for participatory research such as those of legitimacy, representativity, and agency.
5. Stakeholder short interviews (January – March 2023): The mapped stakeholders were contacted to be briefly interviewed and be invited to the Cycle 3 hackathon. The unstructured interviews ranged from 15 to 45 minutes and started with a presentation of the study's objectives, followed by the questions that elicited experts' perspectives about the renewable energy systems' main aspects and role.
6. Cycle 3 hackathon stakeholder workshop (31st May 2023). The main objectives of the workshop were to validate the proposed qualitative storylines with stakeholders and discuss forms of quantification which could take place to link climate and energy variables, as well as the societal concerns.

Figure 1 illustrates the several methods deployed to prepare for the workshop and the activities conducted during the workshop. The full-day workshop brought together experts in re-

Figure 1: Summary of the activities conducted across workshop phases

newable energy systems covering a broad range of perspectives: ranging from academia to policy-makers and also practitioners. This list was based on the purposive stakeholder mapping mentioned above, providing a comprehensive representation of renewable energy from various perspectives, including environment, sociology, and media. Similarly, participants represented companies and research centers from different regions across Spain, such as Valencia, Zaragoza, and Barcelona. These tasks led to invitations being sent to 50 stakeholders, with 22 responding positively to attend the nextGEMS stakeholder event at the Universidad Complutense de Madrid on May 31st 2023.

The day commenced at 11:00, with approximately 12 of the expected 22 stakeholders, who presented their activities related to renewable energies. The primary objective was to encourage networking among participants and identify synergies among projects. Following the initial round of presentations and lunch, Aleks Lacima (BSC) presented a case study concerning wind energy, which drew considerable interest from those present and allowed the participants to have an understanding of the type of data outputs obtainable from nextGEMS models. In the afternoon session (16:00 to 18:00), the workshop commenced with the main goal of revising and operationalizing three qualitative storylines on renewable energy based on the Spanish case and national legislation. Three groups were formed and had highly engaging discussions on the topics. After the workshop, participants were invited to attend a keynote speech by Francisco J. Doblas-Reyes, who introduced [DestinE](#) and the Digital Twins initiative to the wider nextGEMS audience. Two weeks after the workshop, the participants received from the project the main outcomes of the workshop.

Subsequent activities following this workshop will involve operationalizing these storylines using nextGEMS output data, in collaboration with other research centers focused on energy models, and complete the storyline in deliverable D10.8 by month 46.

4.2.2 Storylines of Fisheries pilot study

The type of storyline that will be conducted for the Fisheries case study is the one presented in Shepherd et al., 2018, and it is called, "Physical Climate Storylines". According to the authors, PCS are "physically self-consistent unfoldings of past events, or of plausible future events, that are based on a set of assumptions and built from causal arguments." (Shepherd et al., 2018).

PCS are an alternative form of dealing with uncertainties, providing a fully probabilistic approach.

4.3 Update to the coproduction plan

The original coproduction plan as outlined in the report for [D10.1](#) remains unchanged. Three hackathons were successfully conducted in the first half of the project and the three hackathons for the application phase of nextGEMS are already in the planning/preparation stages.

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6 Dissemination and uptake

6.1 Uptake by the targeted audience

As indicated in the Description of the Action, the audience for this deliverable is:

x	The general public (PU)
	The project partners, including the Commission services (PP)
	A group specified by the consortium, including the Commission services (RE)
	This reports is confidential, only for members of the consortium, including the Commission services (CO)

6.2 This is how we are going to ensure the uptake of the deliverables by the targeted audience

Storylines can be presented in various formats, e.g., web-explorable story-maps, combining text, images and maps with geo-referenced data and simulation output. This type of material is especially adequate for near-field stakeholder groups, the target audience of the nextGEMS storylines, as it involves users additionally in its co-development process. However, we will also use summary reports and progress videos to communicate the key storyline findings to media, a broader audience and policymakers. In particular, the fishery storyline that will apply nextGEMS data to better understand marine ecosystem dynamics and changes in the Atlantic Ocean off the west coast of Africa will also target stakeholders and policymakers from this part of the world. The event where the storyline will be presented to gain most visibility is still under discussion.

7 Deliverable timeliness

Is the deliverable delayed?

no

8 Changes made and/or difficulties encountered, if any

Not applicable.

9 Sustainability

9.1 Links built with other deliverables, WPs, and synergies created with other projects

There is a link with D10.1, D10.2 and D10.3. The basis for effective Communication and dissemination activities are strong links and communication with the whole project.

10 Full track of dissemination activities

- Cycle 1 Hackathon 19. – 22. October 2021 in Berlin

- "Science meets Art" - NextCalendArt 2022
- Office Hour with IBERDROLA on solar energy in January 2022
- UCM Student Hackathon, 01. – 03. April 2022 near Madrid
- Cycle 2 Hackathon 26. June – 02. July 2022 in Vienna
- Storms & Ocean summer slackathon 31. June – 06. July 2022 at the Bornö Institute for ocean and climate studies, Sweden
- "Science meets Art" - NextCalendArt 2023
- Mini-hackathon of Storms & Land at Wageningen University 04. – 06. April 2023
- Cycle 3 Hackathon 29. May – 02. June 2023 in Madrid

11 Full track of publications and IP

Publications within the project can be found on our website: <https://nextgems-h2020.eu/publications/>